

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IRON WITH 3-HYDROXY-1-*p*-SULPHONATOPHENYL-3-PHENYLTRIAZINE

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Fe^{III} forms a bluish black water-soluble complex with 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyl-triazine in the pH range of 2.0 to 4.3, with absorption peaks at 520 and 650 m μ . Full colour development is ensured at 1 : 15 ratio of iron to the reagent. The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 1 to 20 p.p.m. of iron. The molecular extinction coefficient of iron complex at 650 m μ has been determined to be 4.47×10^3 . Nessler's cylinder sensitivity has been found to be 1 part of iron in 5,000,000 parts of solution and spot plate identification limit as 0.1 γ iron in 0.15 c.c. of solution.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine has been reported as a spectrophotometric reagent for palladium (Sogani and Bhattacharyya, *Anal. Chem.*, 1957, 29, 397) and molybdenum (unpublished). It develops an intense bluish black water-soluble colour with Fe (III). This property has been made use of successfully in the spectrophotometric determination of iron in presence of almost all the commonly associated diverse ions. 3-Hydroxy-1-phenyl-3-methyltriazine, possessing identical chelating system, has been recently described for the same purpose (Gupta and Sogani, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 87).

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard Fe(III) solution was prepared by oxidizing 3.920 g. of ferrous ammonium sulphate (A.R.) with hydrogen peroxide in ammoniacal medium and dissolving the precipitated ferric hydroxide in HCl (dil.) before making up the volume to 1 litre (Clowes and Coleman, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1947, p. 187). It was diluted to make a solution containing 25 p.p.m. of iron.

10% HCl (v/v) and 10% sodium acetate (w/v) solutions were used for adjusting the pH. A 0.4% reagent (w/v) solution in distilled water was used.

A Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic-20' was used for measuring the absorption, using 1 cm cuvettes. pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter (model H-2). Visual colour comparisons were made with 50 c.c. Nessler's cylinders.

Absorption Spectra of Iron Complex and the Reagent.—Absorption spectra of 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine and the chelates formed with Fe(III) at different pH values are shown in Fig. 1. Iron solutions (5 c.c. each containing 25 p.p.m.) were taken in two 50 c.c. flasks and varying amounts of HCl and sodium acetate solutions were added so that pH after dilution was 2.7 in one case and 5.1 in the other, followed by the reagent solution (10 c.c.), and the volume made up to the mark. Absorbance was measured with water as reference. A blank solution was prepared in a similar way and its absorbance was measured.

Inspection of the curves shows that at pH 2.7 (Fig. 1, curve 1), the absorbance is maximum at 650 m μ , and at pH 5.1 (curve 2), it is at 520 m μ . This variation in the nature of the curves is indicative of iron complexes of different compositions at different

H^+ -ion concentrations (Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488). $650 m\mu$ was considered a suitable wave-length as there was no interference of the foreign ions in this region.

FIG. 1

Effect of pH on Degree of Complex Formation.—For studying the effect of pH on colour reaction, several solutions containing identical quantities of iron (4 c.c. of 25 p.p.m. iron) and the reagent were prepared, as given above, excepting that different amounts of HCl and sodium acetate solutions were added so that the final pH values ranged from 1.2 to 6.0. Absorbance was measured both at 650 and 520 $m\mu$. Fig. 2 shows the effect of change of pH on complex formation. The range of constant maximum absorbance at 650 $m\mu$ is between pH 2.0 and 4.3. At 520 $m\mu$,

FIG. 2

the constant absorbance is between 2.0 and 4.0 and then it increases. It indicates the formation of an iron complex of different composition.

Effect of Reagent Concentration.—Varying amounts of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ reagent solution were added to a series of solutions containing 5 c.c. of $10^{-3}M$ iron. *pH* was kept at about 2.6. Absorbance was measured at 650 $m\mu$, using water as blank. Full colour development was ensured at 1 : 15 ratio of iron to the reagent.

Development of Colour and Stability of the Complex.—The colour formation of the iron complex with the reagent was almost instantaneous and it retained stability for 42 minutes at 22°. The blue colour of the complex changed to violet in about 4 hours. The fading of the colour is due to the reducing action of the reagent which converts ferric into ferrous and the change in colour is probably due to change in the composition of the complex.

Beer's Law.—Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 1 to 20 p.p.m. of iron at 650 $m\mu$. The molecular extinction coefficient of the iron complex has been calculated to be 4.47×10^3 .

Effect of Temperature.—The colour intensity of the iron complex was slightly decreased with the increase in temperature. However, there was no appreciable difference within 10° of temperature.

Sensitivity of the Reaction.—Sensitivity of the reaction was determined in Nessler's cylinders in the usual way and was found to be 1 of iron in 5,000,000 parts of solution. Spot plate identification limit was found to be 0.17 of iron.

Tolerance of Diverse Ions.—Qualitative testing has shown that As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Ce^{4+} , U^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} , Zr^{4+} , ZrO_2^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Ru^{3+} , Rh^4 , Ir^{3+} , alkali and alkaline earth metals and common anions do not show any colour reaction. There is no colour reaction with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+} , Sn^{4+} and Hg^{2+} at low *pH*, and these ions are not likely to interfere in the spectrophotometric determination of iron. Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Tl^{4+} and molybdate, which develop colour reactions with the reagent at low *pH*, show absorption only between 400 and 500 $m\mu$ and, hence, they do not interfere at 650 $m\mu$ in the determination of iron. Ag^+ and Au^{3+} are slowly reduced by the reagent. Fluoride, phosphate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate and cyanide mask the colour reaction.

TABLE I

Tolerance of diverse ions.

Fe (III) = 4 p.p.m.					
Ions.	Added as	Conc. of ion (p.p.m.)	Ions.	Added as	Conc. of ion.
Co^{2+}	Sulphate	100	Al^{3+}	Sulphate	100
Ni^{2+}	"	100	Cr^{3+}	"	20
Zn^{2+}	"	100	Ca^{2+}	Chloride	100
Mn^{2+}	Chloride	100	MoO_4^{2-}	Sodium	50
Cu^{2+}	Sulphate	100	WO_4^{2-}	"	100
Fe^{2+}	"	100			

In examining the tolerance of various ions, only those elements, which normally occur with iron or are usually present in important alloys of iron, have been employed. Table I records the results obtained. Excepting for chromium and molybdate, where limiting concentrations have been found out we have not tested the tolerance beyond the limit mentioned in the table.

D I S C U S S I O N

Fe(III) may be determined spectrophotometrically by various methods. Selection of the method of determination is not simple. The oldest and the best known is the one using thiocyanate (Ossian, *Pharm. Centr.*, 1837, 13, 205). A more intense colour is obtained when the red colour is developed in 2-methoxyethanol (Winsor, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 453) or by adding 60% by volume of acetone (Woods and Mellon, *ibid.*, 1941, 13, 551). Other reagents used are 7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonic acid (Yoe and Hall, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 872), nitroso⁴dimethyl-dihydroresorcinol (Shome, *Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 1205), disodium 1:2-dihydroxybenzene-3:5-disulphonate (Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111), salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde, etc.

Numerous new reagents continue to be proposed. The following have been selected as most worthy of mention, which are reported during the last 4 years. Fe (III) develops a red colour with 3-sulphoanthranilic acid (Zehner and Sweet, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 198), purple colour with 2-fluorobenzoic acid (Buchanan and Wagner, *ibid.*, 1957, 29, 754), red-violet colour with ethylenediamine-bis (sulphosalicylaldehyde) (Mukherjee, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, 13, 268), red colour with thenoyltrifluoroacetone (Kingdom and Mellon, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 860) and blue colour with 4-amino-4-methoxydiphenylamine (Erdey and Szabadvary, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1955, 6, 131). 3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazine is one more addition to the list of good spectrophotometric reagents for iron. No claim for its superiority over other reagents is made.

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